

DISPARITIES IN MANAGERIAL BEHAVIOR – ARE MEN AND WOMEN MANAGERS BEHAVING IN THE SAME WAY?

Dr. SADAF NAZ

Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Hazara University Mansehra, Pakistan.

Dr. SAGHIR AHMAD CH

Department of Education, Hazara University Mansehra, Pakistan.

Dr. AYESHA BATOOL *

Assistant Professor, Lahore College for Women University Lahore, Pakistan.

*Corresponding Author Email: drayesharana19@gmail.com

ANJUM QAYUAM

Department of Education, Hazara University Mansehra, Pakistan.

Abstract

This study examines the difference between men and women managers concerning their managerial behavior. The managerial styles of male and female department heads were compared in this quantitative study. To fulfill the intended goals of the study, a survey was carried out. The 262 participants of both genders and 131 department heads—25 of whom were female and 106 of whom were male- provided the data. The information was gathered using questionnaires on a five-point Likert scale. The collected data were analyzed by applying descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study showed that both men and women managers behave in the same way they do not differ in their general perceptions as a manager and no significant difference was found in their managerial behavior. Women, as compared to men, were less in number in top management positions. It is therefore recommended that the government allow managers, both male and female, to have equal possibilities to become top managers.

Keywords: Gender Differences, Managerial Behavior, Men and Women Managers.

INTRODUCTION

The fields of business and finance gave rise to the term management. The art of managing a business with external assistance is known as management. Since management is a global process, it does not adhere to any strict guidelines or set patterns that require activity at all times. Reaching the organization's goals is the primary responsibility of management. The process of establishing and preserving an atmosphere where individuals collaborate in teams and accomplish their objectives is known as management. Planning, organizing, inspiring, and supervising others' work to accomplish organisational goals and objectives are within the review of management (Mehdinezhad & Sardarzahi, 2015).

In an organization, a manager's behavior towards his subordinates is reflected in his managerial style. It is made up of managerial styles, or how they go about things, and managerial functions, or what they do. Any organization's subordinates would respond in kind to a manager's activities. On the other hand, the organization's manager would respond to the acts of their subordinates. Different behavioral aspects are brought about

by the manager's actions and reactions as well as the subordinates' actions and reactions (Batool & Tahir, 2015).

The situation of women is a major concern on a global scale. Their situation includes things like excessive violence, economic empowerment, maternal health, female illiteracy, and low standing in family matters. Worldwide, women's poor status prevents them from being in charge of their own lives. Social stratification and gender inequality are the foundations of the atmosphere that this situation creates. Men are viewed as superior in several social and familial contexts. This phenomenon is prevalent in third-world nations, particularly those in South Asia.

The world's South Asia is a multilingual and cosmopolitan continent. However, gender discrimination is a commonality across many South Asian civilizations and regions. Although a lot has been written about Pakistani women's position, women continue to face hardships in a variety of areas around the nation. One of the South Asian nations with a high rate of gender disparity is Pakistan. On the HDI for gender equality, it is rated 115th out of 187 nations (Rehman, Moazzam, & Ansari, 2020).

Widespread gender inequality in Pakistan leads to deeply ingrained disparities in the home, society, and between childhood and adolescence, women have always faced discrimination in the family sphere. Since investing in her is compared to watering a nearby tree, she is not motivated to pursue an education (Khalid & Frieze, 2004). All that is thought about her is that she ought to be married soon and that her spouse ought to bear the remainder of her bills. Her sole responsibility is to handle household chores that the government does not track. She is given a lowly position in society because of this status. They already play roles that society has set for them.

The family is the only institution that establishes social norms and ethics for the two sexes in patriarchal societies like Pakistan. Fathers, brothers, and husbands are the only people who are thought to be the custodians of women under the current system. In Pakistan as well as other countries, there are fewer women than men in senior managerial roles. Working women in Pakistan face numerous challenges in their pursuit of career advancement due to the country's conservative and predominantly male society. However, working women and women in managerial positions are becoming more accepted by society as a result of the rising literacy rate and increased efforts from the government, civil societies, and media (Sarwar & Abbasi, 2013).

Pakistan's conditions for women are not ideal because of the impact of culture and religion; women are frequently the targets of violence, discrimination, and other severe laws and regulations. Reports from a few prominent international organizations also highlight this situation. For instance, in a 2011 study, the Reuters Foundation listed Pakistan as one of the top five least desirable places in the world for women to live. Additionally, Pakistan underperformed on all developmental indices as reported by the Global Gender Gap Report, (Hausman, Tyson, & Zahidi, 2012) including female educational attainment, health facility accessibility, political empowerment, economic involvement, and women's opportunities.

In Pakistan, women have historically taken on the role of family care and have stayed at home most of the time. But things are starting to change in Pakistan, where more women are taking on the dual responsibilities of providing care for their families and working in a variety of professions or as entrepreneurs. The shift can be attributed to advancements in education and societal transparency in general. The status of working women in Pakistan may be described as being at a crossroads, with advancements in their careers being hampered by issues including bullying at work, pay inequality, and discrimination in hiring, on the one hand, and support and developments on the other (Tahir, 2020).

Pakistan is thought to have a more masculine culture than a feminine. Gender roles are more clearly defined in Pakistan. The literature is replete with examples of bias against female managers, including evidence that these managers receive lower ratings than their male counterparts, are not as well-liked, and face consequences for embracing more traditionally masculine leadership philosophies (Elsesser, 2016).

Many qualities of a successful manager, such as ambition, impartiality, and a convincing attitude, have been linked with masculinity (Guney et al., 2006). In a male-dominated country like Pakistan, women have very lower options to make progress as a manager but still, if lower employees and organizations support women managers they can make rapid progress in career development as well and it will improve their quality of life too (Islam, 2004). A number of people believe that women can be disqualified from taking responsible positions in masculine jobs but nowadays women are improving themselves as good manager in masculine jobs too.

Figure 1: Managerial Behavior and its Factors

Research Questions

The focus of this research study was to address the following research questions.

1. What Managerial Behavior practices are used by the heads of departments in universities?
2. What are the perceptions of university teachers regarding HODs' Managerial Behavior practices?
3. What are the differences in perceptions of university teachers about Managerial Behavior practices in terms of demographic variables (gender, age, qualification, designation, management, and teaching experience)?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive design and collected data through a survey methodology. A multistage random sampling technique was used to choose the study's sample. In the initial phase, the investigator deliberately chose universities with multiple female department heads. Thus, the researcher chose the University of Peshawar, University of Swabi, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan, and Hazara University Mansehra as the four universities in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. In the second round, all 131 department heads—25 women and 106 men—were chosen. By proportionate random sampling techniques, a sample of 262 teachers, representing both genders, was chosen for the third stage. Ratios of 1:2 were used to select these teachers. The selection of one department head and two of their staff members was done at random. 131 department heads and 262 teachers made up the sample size in total.

Table 1: Demographic profile of Respondents (N= 131)

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	106	80.9
Female	25	19.1
Marital Status		
Married	123	93.9
Unmarried	8	6.1
Separated/ Divorced	0	0
Age Group		
25-35 years	14	10.7
36-45 years	49	37.5
46-55 years	51	38.9
55+ years	17	12.9
Educational Level		
Master	1	0.7
M.Phil./ MS	14	10.7
PhD	96	73.3
Post Doc	20	15.3
Designation		
Lecturer	5	3.8
Assistant Professor	48	36.7
Associate Professor	44	33.6

Professor	34	25.9
Service		
1-5 years	24	18.3
6-10 years	35	26.7
11-15 years	32	24.4
16-20 years	20	15.3
20+ years	20	15.3
Management Experience		
1-5 years	91	69.5
6-10 years	23	17.5
11-15 years	11	8.4
16-20 years	3	2.3
20+ years	3	2.3

Research Instrument

Questionnaires were used to gather data. With a few minor modifications, a questionnaire was used for department heads and teachers alike.

The questionnaire was divided into five sections: commitment, decision-making, communication, organisation, and motivation.

Each section contained ten statements. Using the indicators Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree, a five-point Likert scale was used to collect responses regarding the managerial behavior of department heads.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The researchers visited the selected universities to gather data, asking participants and department heads to fill out the questionnaire. The respondents were provided with clear instructions on how to complete the questionnaire and research ethics were adhered to.

The respondents were provided with a brief description of the research study's objectives. Before the collection of data, all respondents provided their consent. Respondents' confidentiality and privacy were ensured.

On the first try, seventy percent (70%) of the responses were obtained. Reminders increased the number of responses by twenty percent (20%). Email and WhatsApp were the methods used to receive four percent (4%) of the replies.

The researcher's data collection process took four months. 94.6% of the respondents responded. The data were analyzed using the mean score, cumulative mean, percentage, t-test, and ANOVA test. Conclusions and recommendations were made in light of the findings.

FINDINGS

Overall, findings could be categorized into three main findings.

(i) Perceptions of HODs and Teachers about Managerial Behavior

HODs perceived their managerial behavior as good and proficient.

Table 2: Factor-wise views of HODs about managerial behavior

Variables	N	Mean	SD
Communication	124	4.45	.419
Organization	124	4.35	.413
Motivation	124	3.81	.480
Decision Making	124	4.39	.454
Commitment	124	4.45	.474

Table 2 shows the HODs' perception of managerial behavior. Mean scores of 4.45, 4.35, 3.81, 4.39, and 4.45 indicate that heads of department were at a high level of agreement with the statements and that they are good in managerial behavior.

Teachers' Perceptions of managerial behavior

Findings revealed that teachers also described the managerial behavior of their HODs as good and proficient. It was discovered that HODs' self-reported managerial behaviors and teachers' observations of those behaviors were comparable in terms of all managerial behaviour components.

Table 3: Factor-wise views of teachers about managerial behavior of their HODs

Variables	N	Mean	SD
Communication	248	4.05	.699
Organization	248	3.92	.695
Motivation	248	3.40	.676
Decision Making	248	3.94	.722
Commitment	248	3.98	.803

The participants' opinions about department heads' managing style are displayed in Table 3. They showed a high degree of agreement with the assertions and their heads of department's good managerial behaviour in terms of communication, organisation, motivation, decision making, and commitment are indicated by their mean scores of 4.05, 3.92, 3.40, 3.94, and 3.98.

(ii) Comparison of HODs' Managerial Behavior on Gender Basis

According to the findings, male and female HODs behave similarly in terms of management. They have the same self-perception, and there is no gender difference in the managerial behaviour of male and female HODs in areas such as organisational commitment, communication, inspiration, and decision-making.

Table 4: Gender Difference Factor wise about HODs managerial behavior

Variables	Gender	N	M	SD	t	df	P
Communication	Male	99	4.43	.412	-.936	122	.351
	Female	25	4.52	.446			
Organization	Male	99	4.33	.428	-1.190	122	.236
	Female	25	4.44	.338			
Motivation	Male	99	3.77	.489			

					-1.633	122	.105
	Female	25	3.95	.422			
	Male	99	4.38	.459			
Decision Making					-.571	122	.569
	Female	25	4.44	.439			
	Male	99	4.43	.467			
Commitment					-.948	122	.345
	Female	25	4.53	.505			

The views of male and female department heads regarding managerial behaviour are compared in Table 4. P values of $0.351 > 0.05$, $236 > 0.05$, $105 > 0.05$, $569 > 0.05$, and $.345 > 0.05$ indicate that there is no statistically significant difference between the opinions of male and female department heads and that they behave in the same way as managers.

(iii) Comparison of HODs' Managerial Behavior in terms of their Demographic factors

The results demonstrated that, with the exception of a group of HODs who are between the ages of 25 and 35 and 46 and 55, demographic factors like age, experience as a chairperson (management experience), qualification, designation, teaching experience, and marital status have no bearing on the overall managerial behaviour of HODs. Marital status also has an impact on commitment. Additionally, group HODs with one to five years and six to ten years of teaching experience have an impact on commitment and communication factors. Department heads with six to ten years and more than twenty years of teaching experience also have an impact on the motivation factor. Based on current quantitative findings, there is generally no discernible difference between the managerial behaviours of male and female heads of departments.

Table 5: Comparative views of HODs' Managerial Behavior in Terms of their Demographic Factors

Variable	Group	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	P
Age	Between	226.384	3	75.461	3.567	0.016
	Within	2538.584	120	21.155		
	Total	27.64.968	123			
Management Experience	Between	92.446	4	23.111	1.334	0.261
	Within	2062.352	119	17.331		
	Total	2154.789	123			
Qualification	Between	4.228	2	2.124	0.119	0.887
	Within	2150.551	121	17.773		
	Total	2154.798	123			
Designation	Between	38.273	3	12.758	0.723	0.540
	Within	2116.526	120	17.638		
	Total	2154.798	123			
Teaching Experience	Between	252.769	4	63.192	3.954	0.005
	Within	1902.029	119	15.983		
	Total	2154.798	123			

The participants participated in the study having different demographic factors. There were significant difference in terms of age and teaching experience regarding managerial behavior but no difference found based on management experience, qualification and designation.

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The current study's objective was to compare and evaluate the managerial philosophies of male and female department heads at Khyber Pakhtunkhwa-based Pakistani universities. The study's findings demonstrated that instructors give a fairly accurate description of their department heads' managerial style. The department heads themselves, however, thought highly of their managerial style. It was discovered that there is no discernible difference between the perspectives of teachers and heads of departments regarding any aspect of managerial behaviour when comparing self-reported managerial behaviors and those perceived by educators. The results indicated that there is no discernible difference between the opinions of department heads and teachers. These results are corroborated by earlier research. According to Mohammadi et al. (2012), teachers and HODs have similar views on managerial behavior.

The study's findings also demonstrated that department heads of both sexes view themselves as managers in terms of their managerial style. This outcome is consistent with Thomas's (2004) study, which discovered that male and female managers behave similarly in their managerial roles and are equally successful, with far more similarities than differences. The study's findings corroborate those of Oshagbemi and Gill's (2003) investigation, which found that managerial behaviour differed little between men and women. Studies on the managerial behaviour of heads have found no discernible differences between the management styles of men and women (Vilkinas & Cartan, 1997; Wajcman, 1996).

According to Billing and Alvesson (1994), the majority of empirical studies reveal modest variations in the management roles held by men and women. The similarities rather than the differences between men and women in management roles are most noticeable when it comes to behaviour, attitudes, etc (p. 50). Nonetheless, the research findings do not align with those of Quitugua (1990) or Naeemullah et al. (2010). In addition, the findings showed that teachers thought highly of both male and female department heads for their managerial style and that biological distinctions should be disregarded in the pursuit of gender parity in the workplace. The study's findings revealed that, except for age and teaching experience, there is no significant relationship between any of the managerial behaviour factors communication, organisation, motivation, decision-making, and commitment and demographic parameters age, teaching experience, qualification, designation, and marital status from the perspective of department heads.

In general, public universities, teachers have positive perceptions of department heads' managerial styles concerning the organizational commitment factor. According to their descriptions, their department heads have a deep sense of kinship and belonging towards their department. They allocate time for meetings and other obligations and complete

their work on schedule. They never compromise on academic matters and arrive on time for work. In general, public universities, the managerial behaviour of male and female department heads is similar. Regarding commitment, organisation, motivation, communication, and decision-making, they share the same opinions. Male and female department heads behave in the same way when it comes to communication management. The study's findings show that there is no significant distinction between the managerial approaches of male and female department heads. The findings of the study showed that both men and women managers behave in the same way they do not differ in their general perceptions as a manager and no significant difference was found in their managerial behavior. Women, as compared to men, were less in number in top management positions. It is therefore recommended that the government allow managers, both male and female, to have equal possibilities to become top managers.

References

- 1) Batool, S., & Tahir, M. (2015). Attitude towards female manager in Pakistan: Evidence from banking, education, and telecom sector. *Dialogue (Pakistan)*, 10(4).
- 2) Billing, Y. D., & Alvesson, M. (1994). *Gender, managers, and organizations* (Vol. 50). Walter de Gruyter.
- 3) Elsesser, K. M. (2016). Gender bias against female leaders: A review. *Handbook on well-being of working women*, 161-173.
- 4) Guney, S., Gohar, R., Akinci, S. K., & Akinci, M. M. (2006). Attitudes toward women managers in Turkey and Pakistan. *Journal of International Women's Studies*, 8(1), 194-211.
- 5) Hausmann, R., Tyson, L. D. A., & Zahidi, S. (2012). The global gender gap report 2012. Geneva: World Economic Forum.
- 6) Islam, N. (2004). Sifarish, sycophants, power and collectivism: Administrative culture in Pakistan. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 70(2), 311-330.
- 7) Khalid, R., & Frieze, I. H. (2004). Measuring perceptions of gender roles: The IAWS for Pakistanis and US immigrant populations. *Sex Roles*, 51(5), 293-300.
- 8) Mehdinezhad, V., & Sardarzahi, Z. (2015). A study of the leadership behaviors reported by principals and observed by teachers and its relation with principals' management experience. *Journal on Efficiency and Responsibility in Education and Science*, 8(2), 48-53.
- 9) Mohammadi, A., Alaie, H., & Pourghaz, A. (2012). Comparing the importance of managerial and leadership behaviors from views of school principals and teachers. *Journal of Educational and Instructional Studies in the World*, 2(2), 130-136.
- 10) Naeemullah, K., Muhammad, I. H., Muhammad, S., Uddin, M. N., & Shafqat, H. (2010). The managerial behavior of secondary school heads in Punjab (Pakistan). *Educational Research and Reviews*, 5(4), 186-189.
- 11) Oshagbemi, T., & Gill, R. (2003). Gender differences and similarities in the leadership styles and behaviour of UK managers. *Women in Management Review*.
- 12) Quitugua, J. A. (1990). *Consistency of principals' leadership styles and teachers' perceptions in the commonwealth of the northern marianas*.
- 13) Rehman, H., Moazzam, D. A., & Ansari, N. (2020). Role of microfinance institutions in women empowerment: A case study of Akhuwat, Pakistan. *South Asian Studies*, 30(1).

- 14) Reuters, T. (2011). *The world's 5 most dangerous countries for women*. Thomson Reuters Foundation Survey.
- 15) Sarwar, F., & Abbasi, A. S. (2013). An in-depth analysis of women's labor force participation in Pakistan. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, 15(2), 208-215.
- 16) Tahir, M. (2020). A qualitative study of Pakistani working women's advancement towards upper level managerial positions. *International Journal of Applied Research in Social Sciences*, 2(1), 31-40.
- 17) Thomas, N. (2004). *The John Adair handbook of management and leadership*. Thorogood.
- 18) Vilkinas, T., & Cartan, G. (1997). How different are the roles displayed by female and male managers? *Women in Management Review*.
- 19) Wajcman, J. (1996). Desperately seeking differences: Is management style gendered? *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, 34(3), 333-349.